

Supplementary Material for the paper: Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning for Traffic Signal Optimization with Swarm of Drones

This document provides a more detailed description of the paper “Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning for Traffic Signal Optimization with Swarm Approach”. The remainder of this document is organized as follows. The main methodology of the simulation is explained in Section 1. Detailed information about the Namur simulation model is presented in Section 2. Section 3 presents the drone flight altitude used to cover the area. Simulation results are shown in Section 4.

1 Methodology

This section presents a comprehensive explanation of the methodology and the relationships between its components. The simulation undergoes two main phases: the training and the evaluation phase, as shown in Fig. 1. In the training phase, the simulation trains a multi-agent DQN using real-time traffic data generated from a simulation of the Belgian city Namur, to minimize the remaining number of vehicles at four intersections with varying road geometries and traffic signal phase configurations. The multi-agent DQN interacts with the Vissim environment, receiving the resulting states that indicate the impact of its actions and the corresponding rewards to guide learning and build a history set. Finally, the main goal of the multi-agent DQN is to define a policy based on historical traffic data that maps the number of vehicles to optimal green light durations, thereby efficiently reducing congestion on interconnected roads between intersections. During the evaluation phase, we assess the performance of the trained multi-agent DQN using the swarm of drones within the Vissim simulation environment. The drones are deployed to collect real-time data based on predefined path planning, which serve as input states for the network to select greedy actions that maximize the expected reward. However, because Vissim does not natively support drone flight simulation; each road segment in the Vissim environment is discretized into fixed-length cells. The vehicle counts within these sub-cells, which form a cellular representation of the road network in the Python environment, are continuously updated based on the traffic flows generated by the Vissim model. This dynamically updated cellular map is then

Figure 1: Methodology and the relationships between simulation components in the training and evaluation phases.

used to guide drone navigation and enables systematic, cell-by-cell traffic data collection by drones. To solve communication problems between the drones and the traffic lights, fixed meeting points have been assigned where drones transmit recently collected data to the traffic lights and receive traffic data about regions outside their paths. The methodology enables each agent to access information from adjacent agents, supporting synchronized operation within the distributed network. Finally, the optimal green time durations are implemented in Vissim to evaluate their performance.

2 Namur Simulation Model

The simulated roads are represented in dark gray, with six traffic inflows connected to the main circular boundary of the layout to model traffic entering the city center as shown in Fig. 2. Due to the limitations of Vissim in supporting drone-based observation, a discrete cellular map is designed to represent traffic data by distributing vehicle counts across subcells. The lengths of the Vissim roads, including Bld. de Chiny, Rue Godefroid, and Bld. Ernest Melot are approximately 360 m, 280 m, and 320 m, respectively. The map divides each road segment into multiple subcells, each measuring 20 meters, covering all directions of traffic flow.

3 Altitude Flight of Drones

The camera is oriented in a nadir (downward-facing) position of the drone with a fixed angle of view. In the cellular model, to ensure complete coverage of a single cell, the drones should fly at specific flight altitudes as follows:

$$h = \frac{cell_{dimension}}{2 \cdot \tan(\theta/2)} \quad (1)$$

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Graphs showing, for the *drones condition*, the green light duration of a) traffic light 1, b) traffic light 3, at all cycles. In both graphs, purple boxes refer to phase 1, green boxes to phase 2, and yellow boxes to phase 3. Each box is made of 10 points corresponding to the 10 evaluation runs. The red numbers on the x-axis indicate the number of communication events between the drones and the traffic light that occurred between the traffic light cycles.

intersection 1 attempts to minimize congestion at both Bld. Ernest Melot and its west direction. When the drone provides data indicating low congestion at Bld. Ernest Melot, the controller focuses on alleviating congestion in the other directions.

Traffic light 3 has instead a constant strategy, which consist three Phases. The green light of phase 3 is longer than the green light of phases 1 and 2 (e.g., see Fig. 3b, yellow boxes, at cycles 1, 2, 3, 4, 5). This strategy is used to reduce the number of vehicles accessing Bld de Chiny, since no vehicles entering intersection 3 in phase 3 make a U-turn in Bld de Chiny, while 50% of vehicles entering intersection 3 in phases 1 and 2 turn right and go straight, respectively, in Bld de Chiny. Since the intersection has three phases and considering the fixed cycle time, there is not much variation in the duration of the green traffic light (e.g., see Fig. 3b). In the first cycle, when no information is available from the drone for the DQN to make a decision, the duration of phase 3 is 40 s, while phases 1 and 2 are set to 18 s (e.g., see first cycle in Fig. 3b). When the information about the number of vehicles on Bld de Chiny is transferred to intersection 3 after cycle 2, the controller tries to adjust all phases of intersection 3 by decreasing the green duration of phase 3 by around 30 s, and increasing phases 1 and 2 by around 27 and 20 s, respectively. This is clear evidence of the coordination between the traffic lights supported by the drones' activity.

In the previous simulation conditions in the paper, at the beginning of each evaluation run, 40 vehicles were randomly positioned on Bld E. Melot and Bld de Chiny, and 20 vehicles on Rue de Godefroid. This corresponds to an initial occupancy of 50 % of the full capacity of each road. To evaluate the efficiency of the proposed traffic monitoring and management system, we run the simulation under worst-case condition by considering 90 % occupancy of the roads at the beginning of the simulation. The system undergoes 10 evaluation runs, and in contrast to the previous condition with different initial vehicle distributions, there is little variation in vehicle placement in this scenario. Each run lasts long enough to allow each traffic light to complete 30 cycles, each cycle lasting 78 s. Fig. 4a refers to the average and standard deviations, over 10 evaluation runs, of the sum of vehicles queuing in Bld. de Chiny while traveling west (in Bld. Ernest Melot) and vehicles queuing in Bld. E. Melot, while traveling east (in Bld. de Chiny), at the end of the green light of phase 1 of traffic light 2. Fig. 4b refers to the average number of vehicles queuing in Rue Godefroid at the end of the green light of phase 2. In both graphs of Fig. 4, the blue line refers to *drones condition*, the orange line refers to *camera condition*, and the green line refers to *control condition*. In all conditions, the number of vehicles queuing at the end of the green light of phase 1 (see Fig. 4a) tends to decrease from 110 vehicles in the first cycles to 35 vehicles by cycle time 8, although with multiple oscillations, over successive cycles. These multiple oscillations occur due to driving behaviors, including lane changing, driving acceleration or deceleration, and delays caused by pedestrian crossings, among other factors. However, the number of vehicles queuing at the end of the green light of phase 2 in Rue Godefroid (see Fig. 4b) remains approximately constant at around 25 vehicles between cycles 1 and 8. This provides evidence that, under fully congested conditions, the priority of

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: (a) Graph showing the average and standard deviations, over 10 evaluation runs conducted with 90 % occupancy at the beginning of the simulation, of: a) the sums of vehicles queuing in Bld. de Chiny while traveling west (in Bld. Ernest Melot) and vehicles queuing in Bld. Ernest Melot while traveling east (in Bld. de Chiny) at the end of the green light of phase 1 of traffic light 2 successive cycles; (b) number of vehicles queuing in Rue Godefroid while traveling either west (in Bld. Ernest Melot) or east (in Bld. de Chiny) at the end of the green light of phase 2 of traffic light 2 successive cycles. In both graphs, the blue line refers to *drones condition*, the orange line to *camera condition*, and the green line to *control condition*.

the management system is to alleviate traffic congestion on Bld. de Chiny and Bld. Ernest Melot, rather than on Rue Godefroid, as these are the main roads of the city and have greater widths.

In *drones condition*, at the beginning of cycle 8, the drones transmit data indicating lower congested traffic conditions on Bld. de Chiny and Bld. Ernest Melot around 40 vehicles. At this time, the DQN focuses on alleviating traffic congestion on Rue Godefroid (see Fig. 4b, blue line, cycle 8 to 12). Then, as the number of vehicles on Rue Godefroid decreases to around 10 at cycle 12, the policy shifts to increase the green duration of phase 1, which leads to an increase in the number of vehicles on Rue Godefroid from cycles 12 to 15 (see Fig. 4b, blue line, cycles 12 to 15). This behavior represents a switching pattern between cycles 8 and 15, indicating that the drone’s condition is not able to operate efficiently in all directions of the intersection due to the high initial occupancy and the input rates from neighboring intersections. From cycle 15 to 30, the controller progressively reducing the number of vehicles queuing at the end of the green light of phase 1 (see Fig. 4a, blue line, cycles 15 to 30) and at the end of the green light of phase 2 (see Fig. 4b, blue line, cycles 15 to 30), by regulating the input and output rates once the initial worst case conditions have been overcome.

In *control condition*, from cycle 8 to the end of simulation, the number of vehicles in Bld. de Chiny and Bld. Ernest Melot at the end of all green light of phase 1 shows a smooth decrease to a normal range of 15 vehicles (see Fig. 4a, green line, cycle 8 to 30). Since the green duration for phases 1 and 2 in *control conditionis* considered as 60 and 18 s respectively, the number of vehicles in Rue Godefroid at the end of all green lights of phase 2 remains relatively constant (see Fig. 4b, green line). This shows that the output rate and input rate on Rue Godefroid are approximately the same. Generally, when the number of vehicles exiting equals the number of vehicles entering, traffic conditions remain stable.

In *camera condition*, from cycles 8 to 12, the number of vehicles in Bld. de Chiny and Bld. Ernest Melot at the end of the green light of phase 1 sharply increases to approximately 60 vehicles (see Fig. 4a, yellow line, cycle 8 to 12). However, during the same cycle interval, the number of vehicles on Rue Godefroid at the end of the green light of phase 2 smoothly decreases from 35 to 20 vehicles (see Fig. 4b, yellow line, cycles 8 to 12). Since each camera registers the highest possible volume of traffic whenever the section of the road closest to the traffic light (within 20 m of distance, corresponding to the camera field of view) is jammed, regardless of the state of traffic further down the road. From cycle 12 to the end of the simulation, the number of vehicles in Bld. de Chiny and Bld. Ernest Melot at the end of the green light of phase 1 goes to a highly congested range of approximately 70 vehicles (see Fig. 4a, yellow line, cycle 8 to 30) and the number of vehicles on Rue Godefroid at the end of the green light of phase 2 smoothly increase to 33 vehicles (see Fig. 4b, yellow line, cycles 12 to 30). In the previous simulation condition, with 50 % occupancy, the *camera condition* exhibited a switching behavior between directions. However, in the current worst-case simulation scenario, due to the lack of communication between adjacent intersections to control input rates and incomplete monitoring

data, the *camera condition* is not able to alleviate traffic congestion, resulting in high congestion in both directions. It can be concluded that, compared to the *camera condition*, the *control condition*, due to its fixed input and output rates, is able to alleviate congestion in at least one direction of intersection 2 without requiring communication between intersections for either strategy. Furthermore, despite exhibiting switching behaviour in some cycle times, the monitoring and management system in *drones condition* was the most effective among the compared systems in reducing vehicle queues at intersection 2.

Fig. 5 gives us the opportunity to appreciate how the DQN controllers, in the *drones condition*, adjust the duration of green light of traffic light 2 and 4, to achieve the reduction in vehicles queuing at light-regulated intersection 2, as shown in Fig. 4. The boxplots in Fig. 5a show that the DQN controller at traffic light 2 remains in a steady pattern with low variability. From cycle 1 to 8, green light phase 1 is longer than green light phase 2; this is used to reduce vehicles queuing at the end of the green light phase 1 in Bld E. Melot and Bld de Chiny (e.g., see Fig. 5a, purple boxes, at cycles 1, 2, 3, 4). The green light duration for phase 1 remains approximately constant at 60 s due to the high traffic volume and priority of Bld E. Melot and Bld de Chiny (see Fig. 4a, cycles 1 to 8) to increase the output rate. When a lower number of vehicles is detected by the drones on Bld E. Melot and Bld de Chiny (see, e.g., Fig. 4a, cycle 8) and transferred to intersection 2, traffic unit decide to decrease the green light duration of phase 1 and increase the green light duration of phase 2 to reduce vehicle queues at the end of this phase on Rue Godefroid by increasing the output rate (see, e.g., Fig. 5a, green boxes, cycles 9, 10, 11, 12). By decreasing the green light duration of phase 1, the output rate decreased, leading to an increase in the number of vehicles queuing on Bld E. Melot and Bld de Chiny (see, e.g., Fig. 4a, cycle 12). From cycle 8 to 15, the system exhibits switching behavior. From cycle 15 to the end of the simulation, phase 2 shows a gradual increase in the green duration (approximately 30 s), while phase 1 exhibits a corresponding decrease (approximately 48 s).

Traffic light 4 is working as the input rate to intersection 2 and Rue Godefroid, in which the green light of phase 2 is longer than the green light of phase 1 (e.g., see Fig. 5b, green boxes, at cycles 2, 3, 4, 5). This strategy is used to reduce the number of vehicles accessing Rue Godefroid, since only 50% of the vehicles entering intersection 4 in phase 2 turn right in Rue Godefroid, while 100% of vehicles entering intersection 4 in phase 1 turn right in Rue Godefroid. From cycle 1 to cycle 8, since traffic light 2 focuses on reducing vehicle queues at the end of its green light phase 1 on Bld E. Melot and Bld de Chiny, intersection 4 attempts to regulate the input rate to Rue Godefroid (e.g., see Fig. 5b). This resulted in a nearly constant number of queuing vehicles on Rue Godefroid, without further congestion, at approximately 25 vehicles (see, e.g., Fig. 4b, blue line). At the beginning of the simulation, the variation in green light duration for phase 2 at intersection 4 is limited because the output rate of Rue Godefroid is fixed. Consequently, intersection 4 attempts to maximize the duration of phase 2 to minimize the inflow. As the simulation progressed and congestion on Bld E. Melot and Bld de Chiny was alleviated, the duration

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Graphs showing, for the *drones condition*, the green light duration of a) traffic lights 2, and b) traffic light 4 at all cycles. In all graphs, purple boxes refer to phase 1 and green boxes to phase 2. Each box is made of 10 points corresponding to the 10 evaluation runs conducted with 90 % occupancy at the beginning of the simulation. The red numbers on the x-axis indicate the number of communication events between the drones and the traffic light that occurred between the traffic light cycles.

of phase 2 at intersection 4 decreased, while phase 1 increased correspondingly. This is clear evidence of the coordination between the traffic lights supported by the drones’ activity.

In addition, Fig. 6 exhibits the duration of the green light of traffic lights 1 and 3, to achieve the reduction in vehicles queuing at light-regulated intersection 2. Traffic light 1 affects the inflow to Bld. Ernest Melot, while traffic light 3 affects the inflow to Bld. de Chiny. The boxplots in Fig. 6a show that the DQN controller at traffic light 1 tries to minimize vehicle travel to Bld. Ernest Melot by increasing the duration of the traffic light phase 2. The behavior of intersection 1 is similar to intersection 4, with the main difference being that the convergence of phase 2 to normal conditions is faster (see, e.g., Fig. 6a and Fig. 5a), because of lower congestion on Bld. Ernest Melot occurs earlier than on Rue Godefroid (see, e.g., Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b). It can be concluded that, in the worst-case scenario, the DQN controller at intersection 1 first attempts to minimize congestion on Bld. Ernest Melot, and second, in its west direction. When the drone provides data indicating low congestion at Bld. Ernest Melot, the controller, focuses on alleviating congestion in the other directions.

The boxplots in Fig. 6b show the durations of the three traffic light phases of intersection 3. The strategy is to control the number of vehicles accessing Bld de Chiny. No vehicles entering intersection 3 in phase 3 make a U-turn in Bld de Chiny, while 50% of vehicles entering intersection 3 in phases 1 and 2 turn right and go straight, respectively, in Bld de Chiny. Therefore, the DQN controller at traffic light 3 tries to minimize vehicle travel to Bld. Ernest Melot by increasing the duration of the traffic light phase 3. In the worst-case scenario for Bld. de Chiny, traffic light 3 maintains the duration of phase 3 at its maximum possible value of 40 s (e.g., see Fig. 6b, yellow boxes, at cycles 1, 2, 3, 4, 5). Generally speaking, we are not allowed to set any green light duration to 0 s; therefore, a minimum green time constraint is imposed. By comparing Fig. 6b with Fig. 3b (where the roads are occupied with 50 % capacity), it can be seen that the DQN in the worst-case condition tries to solve the highly congested traffic in Bld de Chiny by fixing the green duration of phase 3 as maximum. In contrast, under another condition, the DQN adjusts all phases at intersection 3 by decreasing the average green duration of phase 3 to around 30 s and increasing the average durations of phases 1 and 2 to approximately 27 s and 20 s, respectively (e.g., see Fig. 3b). This is clear evidence of the coordination between the traffic lights supported by the drones’ activity.

Fig. 7 allows us to appreciate how the learning process evolves across all four agents (multi-agent DQN system applied to the four intersection traffic control problem), highlighting a general decrease in reward values over the training episodes. Overall, all agents exhibit a general downward trend in total reward values as the number of episodes increases (the total training episode is 3500), indicating that the system is successfully learning to minimize the objective function. Agent 2, which serves as the main optimization objective, demonstrates a steady and significant decrease in the total reward, converging from approximately average 25 in the initial episodes to nearly average 10 at the end of training (see Fig. 7, green plot), thereby confirming effective optimization.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: Graphs showing, for the *drones condition*, the green light duration of a) traffic lights 1, and b) traffic light 3 at all cycles. In all graphs, purple boxes refer to phase 1, green boxes to phase 2, and yellow boxes to phase 3. Each box is made of 10 points corresponding to the 10 evaluation runs conducted with 90 % percent occupancy at the beginning of the simulation. The red numbers on the x-axis indicate the number of communication events between the drones and the traffic light that occurred between the traffic light cycles.

Figure 7: Graph showing the learning process evolves across all four agents during 3500 training episode. While all subplots show a downward trend in rewards, agent 2 has lower fluctuation and faster convergence in comparison with other agents.

This confirms that the learning framework effectively improves performance at the main intersection. Agents 1, 3, and 4, whose rewards are influenced both by their local conditions and by the reward of agent 2, also demonstrate decreasing trends, suggesting that they adapt their policies to support the optimization of agent 2 while maintaining their own performance. Agent 1 exhibits a clear and consistent downward trend with relatively moderate variance (the reward ranges approximately between 20 and 40 before episode 2500, and then stabilizes within the interval of 10 to 20 thereafter) indicating stable learning and strong adaptation to both its local environment and the influence of agent 2. It exhibits a trend similar to agent 2, though convergence is achieved at a slower rate (Fig. 7, dark blue plot).

Agent 3, on the other hand, displays higher variability throughout the training process and a slower rate of convergence (the reward ranging from near 15 up to around 45). Although its reward eventually decreases after episode 2000 (the reward stabilizes in the range of approximately 5–15), the fluctuations indicate that it experiences a more complex or less directly influenced traffic pattern, making its learning process less stable compared to the other agents (e.g., see Fig. 7 light blue plot). Agent 4 shows significant fluctuations during the early stages of training (the reward ranging from near 5 up to around 35), which can

be attributed to intensive exploration; however, as training progresses, the variance reduces, and the reward stabilizes at a lower level (the reward stabilizes in the range of approximately 5–10), indicating successful convergence (e.g., see Fig. 7 purple plot). Overall, Agents 1, 3, and 4 demonstrate the ability to adapt their policies not only based on their individual rewards but also under the influence of agent 2, leading to coordinated behavior across the network. The differences in convergence speed and variability among these agents reflect the heterogeneity of traffic conditions and the varying degrees of interaction with the primary optimized intersection.